

GINNNGER

From Barriers to Action

Policy Insights for Advancing Urban
Regeneration in **Italy**

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About GINNGER

The GINNGER project aims to create new, inclusive and participatory processes for **neighbourhood regeneration**. A **methodology** to support collaborative **decision-making** is at the project's core. GINNGER is also designing and implementing regeneration plans across six pilot sites in Europe. Four key areas of regeneration are involved: energy efficiency, renovation of buildings and urban spaces, efficient use of resources and sustainable mobility.

**GINNGER | Co-designing
neighbourhood regeneration**

The Italian policy context

Sustainable and inclusive **neighbourhood regeneration** is shaped by various European hard- and soft-law instruments. However, translating these EU objectives into practice often faces **fragmented competencies** across governance levels, limited integration of **participatory processes** in planning and limited **administrative capacity** at the municipal level.

Italian legislation on this topic includes:

- Law 120/2020 – Simplification Decree¹ (supports regeneration).
- Legislative Decree 42/2004 – Cultural Heritage Code.²
- National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP) urban regeneration measures.³

Barriers, Opportunities and Recommendations

	Barriers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heritage protection constraints and subsequent limits to energy renovation in historic districts. • Lack of clear national guidance and of clear legal instruments for energy communities and energy upgrades in protected buildings. • Non-standardised approaches for balancing conservation requirements and energy performance, with a subsequent increase in costs and risks. • Lack of technical capacity to manage processes without external support, especially in small municipalities.
	Opportunities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong legislative and financial framework (including NRRP and national incentives) for the energy-efficient renovation of buildings and the sustainable development of infrastructure. • Possibility of energy efficiency improvements in protected or historic buildings, thanks to existing laws. • Growing attention to adaptive reuse and circular heritage restoration. • Growing interest and financial support for sustainable mobility and the development of energy communities.
	Recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjust policy for renewable energy communities including administrative simplification, legal and contractual templates for contractors to reduce legal uncertainty, a clear role of local authorities and facilitators, and the introduction of capacity-building and advisory services for municipalities and citizens. • Introduce simplified and standardised authorisation procedures for energy efficiency measures in historic buildings, with clear national or regional guidelines. • Develop pre-approved technical solutions for common interventions on historic buildings (e.g. insulation, renewables) compatible with heritage protection. • Update road and mobility regulations to prioritise active mobility over private car traffic, especially for short urban and peri-urban distances. • Develop and integrate cycling and pedestrian infrastructure with railway stations and alongside high-traffic roads.

Conclusions and next steps

The recommendations presented are **based on GIUNGER's pilot of Orte's experience**. They aim to support authorities and policymakers in facilitating and standardising neighbourhood renovation and collaborative decision-making at the national and local level. Over the coming months, the project partners will expand this analysis, identifying best practices and potential areas for harmonisation across all pilot sites and in all four key areas of regeneration (energy efficiency, renovation of buildings and urban spaces, efficient use of resources and sustainable mobility).

Methodology

The analysis presented was based on data collected through the assessment of policy and regulatory drivers and barriers (conducted under GIUNGER's Task 2.4), and through questionnaires circulated among pilot partners.

Sources and further information

¹ [Legge e testo coordinato 11 settembre 2020, n. 120 - Conversione in legge, con modificazioni, del decreto-legge 16 luglio 2020, n. 76, recante misure - Infoparlamento](#)

² [Dlgs 42/04](#)

³ [Il Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza \(PNRR\) - MEF](#)

Policy Brief
January 2026

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